

Synthetic Data
Working Group

Workshop Findings for Generating & Evaluating Private Synthetic Data in Secure Environments

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Data Portal

Building Responsible Artificial Intelligence in Neuroscience

Risk Evaluation Community Group

Introduction

Dementias Platform UK (DPUK) and the AI Risk Evaluation Group hosted a workshop to bring together Trusted Research Environments (TREs), researchers, and public members to discuss the role of synthetic data and how it can be effectively evaluated for release from TREs.

The DPUK Data Portal is a TRE which enables access to pseudonymised sensitive datasets within a secure environment, to protect privacy while allowing important research to take place. As a TRE, we are interested in how synthetic data can be used for a number of different purposes, such as researcher training, and to ensure the continued protection of privacy in sensitive datasets.

The AI Risk Evaluation Group was established with funding from DARE UK to investigate the risks that AI models developed on TRE data pose and how they can be mitigated. From this group, we found that synthetic data was one of the better methods for preserving-privacy in AI models, and the method researchers felt most comfortable using. The Synthetic Data Working Group was established as an extension of this group to help develop guidance and standards around the use of synthetic data in TREs.

This report showcases the findings from our first meeting on evaluating privacy in synthetic datasets, and provides recommendations for TREs on the use of synthetic data for privacy purposes. Future meetings will evaluate the role of synthetic data for mitigating bias and improving robustness in AI models.

Lewis Hotchkiss
Research Officer

“The Synthetic Data Working Group hopes to unlock the potential of synthetic data by establishing consensus on how we can safely use synthetic data for a range of purposes in TREs and ensure it is private enough.”

Contributors

What is Synthetic Data?

Synthetic data is artificially created data, typically created by generative models trained on real world datasets. Synthesiser models aim to learn the statistical properties, distributions and correlations of the real data, to be able to create realistic artificial samples which are statistically similar to the data it was trained on.

As an example, lets say we have a real dataset of people (illustrated in figure 1) composed of four different characteristics – trouser colour, top colour, gender and hairstyle – and we want to be able to generate synthetic samples based off this data.

Typically, in synthetic data we want good quality and this usually means the distributions and correlations still roughly match in the synthetic data compared to the real. So if in the real data yellow was the most popular top colour, then we'd want this to be approximately true in the synthetic data as well. We also want to keep associations, for example there may be a correlation between gender and hairstyle. But we may get slight differences in these depending on how well the synthesiser is able to learn the properties of the real data.

Figure 3 (Generating Synthetic Data Example)

So we can train a synthesiser model to generate samples which look and feel like the real data, but are not exact copies. This makes synthetic data useful for a number of different purposes. One of these purposes is for improving robustness and mitigating bias in analysis. For example, if you have very few cases of females in your real data, you can use synthetic data to boost minority classes so you have a more balanced and representative dataset. Additionally, synthetic data can also be used to anonymise datasets and create private data which no longer has to comply with GDPR regulations, therefore allowing greater accessibility. If there are few examples of females in the real dataset, then this means they are more likely to be identified as they are more unique. In synthetic data, by increasing these samples, we can reduce that risk.

There are typically two common methods for generating synthetic data – **Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)** and **Variational Auto-Encoders (VAEs)**, both of which aim to create realistic artificial samples by learning the properties of the real data.

GANs are the most common approach and contain two neural networks which compete with each other – a generator which learns how to create realistic new samples, and a discriminator which learns to differentiate between real and fake samples. This aim of the GAN architecture is to be able to generate realistic enough samples that the discriminator can no longer tell the difference between what's real and what's synthetic. This often leads to high quality data which is very similar to the real data.

Figure 2 (Generative Adversarial Network Architecture)

The other common method, **VAEs** also contain two components – an encoder which converts input into a smaller, dense representation called the latent space, and a decoder which takes a sample from the latent space and reconstructs it back into the original data format. Essentially, trying to generate data that looks like the input data by sampling the latent space.

Figure 3 (Variational Auto-Encoder Architecture)

Both of these synthesiser methods aim to create high quality generated data which is statistically similar to the real data. However, if we want higher privacy protections, there may be some additional steps that we need to take improve the privacy guarantees of the generated data.

The Privacy vs Utility Trade-Off

When generating synthetic data, there is a privacy/utility trade-off that exists, where the more private the data becomes, the less utility that data has.

It is common in data privacy practices that there is a trade-off between how private the data is, and how useful it is. This is because the more the data becomes anonymised, the more it loses the ability to provide any meaningful information. The same holds true for synthetic data where the more we move away from what's represented in reality, the less likely that synthetic sample represents the real data.

Figure 4 (Illustration of the Privacy/Utility Trade Off)

If we look at the space of real and synthetic data points in figure 5, representing how similar they are to each other. When we're generating highly private synthetic data, we don't want unauthentic high-quality samples, as they are so similar to the real data points, that there is no privacy protection. If we're generating high utility data, we don't want lots of noisy samples which don't represent the real space, and therefore lose any meaningful correlations and statistical properties. But what we ideally want when we're generating any synthetic data, are authentic high-quality samples which represent the real space, but are different enough that they protect privacy.

Figure 5 (Space of Real & Synthetic Data Points)

Differential Privacy

Differential Privacy is a privacy guarantee that ensures that the presence or absence of a single individual's data doesn't affect the results of an output of that data.

This mathematical framework, not work enables algorithms to not be affected by any one individual, and therefore, you can't determine whether an individual was included in the original dataset or not. In a differentially private algorithm, the output of the function doesn't vary depending on whether an individual is present or not, no matter how unique that individual is. A key feature of this framework is that holds true regardless of knowledge or resources an adversary may have, and is therefore future proof to new methods or knowledge that becomes available.

Figure 6 (Differential Privacy)

This level of guarantee that the algorithm's output distribution for a given dataset will not change significantly if an individual is present or not is called epsilon, or the "privacy budget". This is measured as the maximum distance between a query on a dataset with participant x, and the same query on a dataset without participant x.

Selecting the value for epsilon depends on the dataset, but generally:

- A **smaller** epsilon will provide more similar outputs, and therefore provide higher privacy
- A **larger** epsilon will allow less similarity in outputs, and therefore provide less privacy

So a smaller epsilon will provide higher privacy but less accurate outputs.

There are several mechanisms which exist for achieving differential privacy, with the most common being to add carefully calibrated noise to mask the contribution of any possible individual in the data, while still preserving the overall accuracy of the analysis. There are two ways of doing this – global differential privacy, where noise is added to the output of the algorithm, and local differential privacy where noise is added to the inputs.

We can incorporate differential privacy into synthetic data generation models to ensure the samples which are generated are private. There are several DP-GAN methods for doing this which essentially add noise to the gradients during the training process, to prevent the models from learning too much about the training data. Additionally, other methods exist such as PATE-GAN which applies the Private Aggregation of Teacher Ensembles (PATE) framework to the generator to ensure a differentially private discriminator. Generally, the PATE-GAN method offers robust privacy guarantees with good levels of utility compared to other DP generative methods.

Figure 7 (Differentially Private GAN Architecture)

We can adjust the differential privacy parameters of the model, such as the privacy budget (epsilon), to control the level of privacy in the model. Additionally, we can adjust delta which accounts for the possibility of a privacy breach occurring, so allows for slightly looser privacy guarantees but can significantly improve the utility. Another parameter that can be adjusted is lambda, which controls the scale of noise that is added to the model.

Use Cases of Private Synthetic Data

Synthetic data has lots of potential in sensitive healthcare datasets to help preserve privacy for a number of different purposes where we may want to release data from controlled environments. This may be to create datasets for researcher training, to test workflows before gaining access to the real data, or for training private AI models. However, all of these purposes have the same general governance considerations when it comes to effectively judging privacy to ensure it is safe enough to be released from that environment.

Depending on these use cases, the level of privacy/utility we need will change according to the purpose that the synthetic data will be used for. If we're generating synthetic data for the purpose of training private AI models, we need to make sure there is high utility otherwise that model will be useless. Alternatively, if we want to use synthetic data for researchers to be able to learn how to analyse data before accessing the real data, then utility may not be as much of a consideration, as meaningful analysis isn't needed at that point. We can categorise these two different cases of synthetic data as high fidelity (which is good quality and statistically useful) and low fidelity (where the data is structurally similar, but has lost statistical meaning).

The examples shown in figure 8 show the uses cases highlighted in the workshop. All of these different uses cases require different levels of fidelity, so it is important to consider context when generating synthetic data.

Figure 8 (Uses Cases of Private Synthetic Data)

Low Fidelity

Data Discovery: Before gaining access to real datasets, it is often difficult for researchers to get an idea of what the data looks like and what sort of features it contains. Synthetic data could alleviate this problem to allow researchers to view what the data could look like before applying for access.

Federated Queries: Synthetic data could be used in scenarios where researchers don't have direct access to real data such as in federation. In this scenario, utility isn't much of a priority as researchers only need to know how the data is structured to be able to develop their code and run queries. However, as this is often done in controlled environments, then maybe we don't have to be as concerned about privacy compared to publically releasing synthetic data.

Developing Workflows: We can also use synthetic data to give to researchers before they have full data access so they can develop their workflows while waiting, sometimes months, for full governance approval. For this, some level of utility may be beneficial so that they can get an idea of relationships between certain features.

High Fidelity

Researcher Training: Due to restrictions on sensitive datasets, it is often difficult to learn how to analyse healthcare data as there are very few openly accessible datasets which can be used for this purpose. By generating synthetic datasets, we can use these for researchers to be able to learn how to handle healthcare data, without having to access the real data. In this context, having a good level of utility is necessary to be able to perform some basic analysis. From the workshop, it was also discussed that it would be useful containing the difficult data like missing value or problem values so researchers can learn how to deal with these. But this may introduce privacy concerns depending on the data.

Private AI Models: When developing private AI models, we need very high utility, as these models have the potential for implementation, so the performance of these models needs to be minimally affected.

In high fidelity purposes, it was agreed that differentially private methods which have robust privacy guarantees offer relatively high privacy in synthetic data, while retaining a good level of utility for analysis or developing AI models. Therefore, any generation methods for creating synthetic data for these purposes, should be differentially private and thoroughly evaluated (which will be discussed in the evaluation section of this report).

In the case of low fidelity purposes, it was discussed that the use of artificial data created from metadata, rather than synthetic data trained on real data, may be more beneficial. For these purposes, we only care about the basic structure of the data such as the data types of columns, and the kind of values which exist within them. The correlations and statistical properties of the data don't matter as much.

So instead of training a generative model to create low fidelity synthetic samples, we can use publically available metadata about the dataset to sample the range of values for each variable. Table 1 shows an example of the standardised metadata that DPUK holds for each dataset in the Data Portal.

For each variable, we have the:

- range of values if it is a numerical variable, or the categories if it is a categorical variable
- type of data to show whether it is a categorical, float, integer or datetime type
- completeness to show how many records have a value for that variable (i.e. percentage of non empty values)

Dataset Metadata

Variable Name	Value Range	Data Type	Completeness
Age	33.8 – 92.1	Float	100%
Diagnosis	[0, 1, 2]	Category	89%
MMSE	16 – 30	Integer	75%
...

Table 1 (Example of a subset of metadata for a dataset)

We also have the size of the dataset, so how many rows and columns exist. Because of all of this information we have for each dataset, we can easily use this to create artificial samples which don't use the real data at all, and only publically available information about the dataset. This can be done by drawing random values within the value range which adhere to the particular data type. This means that we have artificial data which represents the basic structure and data types which can be used for low fidelity purposes such as testing queries in federation or developing algorithms.

Therefore, it was determined, that in low fidelity purposes, this would be the preferred method of generating artificial samples as it has less restrictions and hence makes accessibility easier as there are no governance considerations.

However, there may be cases where we require low fidelity versions of synthetic data which preserve some of the correlations and statistical properties of the data for purposes such as researcher training. In this case, we should generate highly private synthetic data with high levels of privacy guarantees.

Figure 9 (SynthOpt Framework)

Generation Framework

The DPUK Data Portal has developed a synthetic data framework called SynthOpt which enables the generation and evaluation of synthetic data, and measurement of the privacy/utility trade off. Optimisation is built around this to enable the generation of different levels of fidelity depending on the purposes of the synthetic data needed.

This framework has been built to be as flexible as possible for the generation of different levels of synthetic data. First of all, the user is able to upload a dataset which will then be pre-processed for the generation process. This involves automatically generating metadata so the synthesiser knows the datatypes of the columns.

The user is then able to select certain parameters for the generation such as the type of model, differential privacy parameters such as the privacy budget (epsilon), and which features may be sensitive or key. This enables the generator to ensure features are protected in the training process and privacy is protected for individuals.

Quality, utility and privacy metrics are then generated, with summary scores given for each to give an overview of the level of the data created. These metrics can be used to determine whether the data is adequate enough for its intended purpose, or if optimisation is chosen, they will be used to optimise the process. Then finally the user is able to download the created model and data.

This framework also incorporates optimisation so that weights can be assigned for privacy and utility to create a synthesiser best suited for the purpose its being trained for. For example, if we want a higher privacy model, we can assign the weights 0.8/0.2 so that it assigns higher priority to maximising the privacy score of the synthesiser compared to utility.

Bad Score, Medium Score, Good Score

Figure 10 (Evaluation Report)

Evaluation Report

Figure 10 shows an example evaluation report generated from the framework. At the top we have the whole table metrics which are coloured to show whether they are good, medium or bad scores. We then have summary scores for fidelity, utility and privacy which contains the combined scores, with appropriate weights, for their respective metrics. For more details, column specific metrics can be viewed to investigate which features may be the most impacted. Figure 11 shows an explanation of the quality and utility metrics used and pages 13-14 shows the privacy metrics used.

This report gives a good overview of the synthetic data that has been created and whether it meets the purpose its been generated for. For example, if we want to generate high utility data, we can adjust the input parameters of the synthesiser model to try and increase the utility score. This can be done manually, or by using the optimisation which is utility weighted so that the framework can find the best input parameters itself. Users also have the option to display distributions and correlations for given features to see how similar the statistical properties are compared to the real data.

Figure 11 (Quality & Utility Metrics)

Evaluating Privacy

Privacy is the biggest consideration when evaluating synthetic data for release from secure environments. GDPR anonymisation practices requires the evaluation of the risk of singling out, inference and linkability when determining if data is anonymised.

These three measures were determined to be the most important metrics when evaluating privacy in synthetic data as they allow us to determine whether the synthetic data complies with GDPR anonymisation. However, it was noted that current anonymisation regulations may not be enough for determining the privacy risk of a dataset, so we cant solely trust these metrics on their own when evaluating synthetic data.

Singling Out

This metric is used to determine the risk of an individual being identified by having unique features compared to the rest of the dataset. This risk increases with the amount of features for the individual as it means they're more likely to be unique. This is why data minimisation is also important to consider when performing analysis or developing AI to ensure no more features than necessary are being used.

Inference

This metric refers to the risk of being able to infer features or membership of an individual, usually where there is knowledge of some existing features about that individual. This can be measured by training an AI model on the synthetic data to infer real sensitive features of the original dataset. The score is calculated based on the true value and predicted value of the sensitive feature in the original dataset.

Linkability

An individual may not be identifiable from a single dataset, but if their attributes can be linked to external datasets, then the linking of those datasets could identify that individual. For example, we could combine a dataset with data from public records if we're able to find overlapping attributes. We can measure this risk by identifying the most similar records in the synthetic data to a target from only looking at a subset of the data which we may know from an external dataset.

Other Metrics for Ensuring Privacy

There are a couple of additional privacy metrics which are useful to use when evaluating synthetic data. One of these is to look for **exact matches** where we can look at how novel the synthetic samples are (i.e. whether there are any exact matches where the features are the same for a record in both the synthetic and real). We can add a degree of variation to this as well so that we can look for values which are very similar like 30.23 and 30.28.

Another metric we can use is to measure the similarity of data points by looking at the **nearest neighbours**. Before training the synthesiser model, we can split the real data into a training set and a holdout set so we have a separate dataset to compare which hasn't been used in the generation process.

If the nearest holdout and training data points are just as close as the synthetic sample then privacy is protected and utility is maintained.

If the nearest training data point is closer than the holdout then this means the synthetic sample is similar to the real data, and therefore privacy is compromised.

If the nearest holdout data point is closer than the training then this means the synthetic sample is too different from reality so utility is compromised.

Figure 12 (Nearest Neighbours Similarity)

All of these metrics allow us to effectively evaluate privacy in synthetic data, and provide quantifiable risk scores for determining whether synthetic data is safe enough for release or not. However, from the workshop a key challenge highlighted was not having common thresholds for determining whether the scores are high enough or not, so there's still a degree of subjectivity when determining risk and interpreting the results.

Ensuring Transparency

To be able to assess synthetic data, the generation and evaluation process needs to be as transparent as possible for data providers to be able to make informed decisions.

During the workshop, it was discussed that we need ways to make the process of creating synthetic data transparent, and explaining the results in a simple and meaningful way for people who may not have the technical knowledge to understand. It was suggested that there is a need for a common framework for documenting the generation process of synthetic data and explaining the evaluation metrics in a standardised way. This would ensure that data providers are fully aware of how that synthetic data has been created and whether the privacy risks have adequately been reduced.

This standardised documentation for the generation process should contain key details including:

- The purpose/context for generating the synthetic data
- Original dataset used in the training process
- Data pre-processing steps
- Selected model
- Model parameters

For the evaluation of the data, the key metrics mentioned should be adequately demonstrated and explained in a sense which is understandable to a lay person. As common threshold values don't exist, these values should be provided in context as to what would typically be considered high and low values, and where the calculated metric value sits on that spectrum.

All of this should additionally be accompanied by the code developed.

Future Work

This report provides the foundational background for progressing guidance and recommendations on synthetic data for privacy.

Future work of this group will investigate:

- Whether we can determine common thresholds for evaluation metrics
- Develop a standardised framework for documenting the generation and evaluation process
- Decide which purposes synthetic data may not be justified and in what contexts do we actually require high fidelity data
- Create learning materials to provide an understanding of what synthetic data is and how it is evaluated
- Balancing the privacy/utility trade-off
- Engaging with data controllers and understanding what level of evidence is needed to feel comfortable with the release of synthetic versions of their data